

Research Article

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis of Bioactive Compounds in Methanolic Fruit Extract of *Garuga pinnata* Roxb

Rudrakshi B. Raut^{*1}, Shivprasad D. Mahadkar²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, S.D. Arts, V.S. Apte Commerce and M.H.Mehta Science College, Palghar-401404, Maharashtra, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, Dr. Shantilal Dhanji Devsey Arts College, Commerce and Science College, Wada-421303, Maharashtra, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08 Sept 2023

Accepted: 09 Sept 2023

Published: 15 Sept 2023

Keywords:

GC-MS analysis, *Garuga pinnata*, Bioactive compounds, Wild Edible Plants, Palghar district

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.8349373

ABSTRACT

Garuga pinnata (Roxb.) is one of the plant species reported from Palghar district of Maharashtra, belongs to the family Burseraceae with ethno-botanical values and is well-known for their Ethno-medicinal applications. It is commonly known as “Kakad” (Marathi). The present investigation was carried out to characterize the bioactive compounds present in methanolic fruit extract of *Garuga pinnata* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrum (GC-MS) method. The results of GC-MS analysis provide different peaks determining the presence of 25 bioactive compounds. The major bioactive compounds 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural, 1,2,3-Benzenetriol, beta-D-Glucopyranose, 1,6-anhydro, Quinic acid, Butanoic acid, octyl ester, n-Hexadecanoic acid and cis-13,16-Docosadienoic acid and minor compounds were also present. Majority of the compounds were belonging to acid group. Hitherto no reports exist on the Phytochemical analysis of *Garuga pinnata* (Roxb).

INTRODUCTION

Over the last few decades, use of herbal drugs has been emphasized due to their easy availability, therapeutic potential, least side effects and minimum cost. At present nearly 80% of the world population rely on plant based drugs for their

health care need. Various plants still available in the nature are yet to be explores for their medicinal potential. (Gosh *et al.* 2015). In the last few years, gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) has become firmly established as a key

***Corresponding Author:** Rudrakshi B. Raut

Address: Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, S.D. Arts, V.S. Apte Commerce and M.H.Mehta Science College, Palghar-401404, Maharashtra, India

Email ✉: dollybraut@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

technological platform for secondary metabolite profiling in plant species.

Garuga pinnata Roxb. (Family: Burseraceae) is a deciduous tree reaching 50ft in height, with bark peeling off in flakes. Leaves are Pinnate, 6-18 in. long with 6-10 pairs of leaflets, opposite. Flowers are small, polygamous, creamy white or yellow, 4 mm across, in axillary panicles to 15 cm; bracts linear to 2 mm; calyx campanulate, tomentose, deciduous; lobes 5, ovate; petals 5, oblong-lanceolate, tomentose, thickened and inflexed at apex; disc crenate, yellow; stamens 10, inserted on calyx tube; filaments 1.5 and 2.5 mm, pubescent; ovary superior, globose, pilose, 5-celled, ovules 2

Photo plate 1: Fruits of *Garuga pinnata* Roxb.

in each cell; style pubescent; stigma 5-lobed. Fruits a drupe, oblong or irregularly globose, greenish-yellow. The fruits are eaten raw or pickled.

A detailed literature review on the plant in investigation has shown that so far there are no published reports worldwide, related to the possible chemical components of "*Garuga pinnata*" Roxb. So, the present study was aimed to investigate the possible bioactive compounds by first preparing the methanolic extract and identification of the compounds by subjecting it to GC-MS analysis.

Photo plate 2: Flowers of *Garuga pinnata* Roxb.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Material:

The fully matured Fruits of *Garuga pinnata* (Roxb.) were collected from Palghar district, Maharashtra, India. A Voucher specimen was deposited in the herbarium of Department of Botany, Sonopant Dandekar College, Palghar.

Preparation of Plant extract:

The Fruits of *Garuga pinnata* were used for preparation of extract. Five gram of oven dried powder were taken in a 250 ml flask and mixed

thoroughly with 50 ml of 100% methanol (pure methanol). Methanolic extract were obtained in an electric shaker (Remi Rotary Shaker, Mumbai, India) for 48 hour in ambient condition (shaking intensity 120 rpm). The extract were then filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper. Filtrate is then concentrated till dry residue was remained. After weighing the residue, respected amount of methanol was added to make the final solution. This solution were further used for GC-MS for analysis.

Photo plate 4: Filtration process

Photo plate 3: Fruit Powder of *G. pinnata*

Photo plate 5: Final solution

GC-MS analysis of bioactive compounds from wild edible plants:

The methanolic extract obtained from fruit of *Garuga pinnata* were subjected to Gas chromatography- Mass Spectroscopy for the determination of bioactive volatile compounds. Some of the important features are summarized below.

GC-MS analysis of the sample were carried out using Shimadzu Make QP-2010 with non-polar 60 M RTX 5MS column. Helium was used as the carrier gas and the temperature programming was

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

set with initial oven temperature at 40⁰C and held for 3 min and the final temperature of the oven was 48⁰C with rate at 10⁰C [Min.sup.-1]. A 2 μL sample was injected with split less mode. Mass spectra was recorded over 35-650 amu range with electron impact ionization energy 70 eV. The total running time for a sample is 45 min. The chemical components from the methanolic extract plant were identified by comparing the retention indices. Quantitative determinations were made by relating respective peak areas to TIC areas from the GC-MS.

Figure 1. GC-MS Chromatogram of Methanolic Fruits extract of *Garuga pinnata* (Roxb.)

The results of GC-MS analysis of methanol extract revealed the presence of 08 Major compounds and 17 Minor compounds. These identified compounds with their retention time (RT), Molecular Formula, Molecular weight and Concentration (Peak area %) are Presented in Table.1 and Table 2. The GC-MS chromatogram

of Major 08 Compounds with their chemical structures is depicted in Figure 1. The GC-MS Spectrum Confirmed the Presence of 08 Components with the Retention time; 14.248, 17.348, 23.877, 25.526, 29.543, 35.029, 35.788 and 39.615.

Retention Time (Min)	% Area of Peak	Compound Analyzed	Molecular Formula	Mol.Wt. (In grams)	CAS Number	Functional Group
14.248	2.40	4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl	C ₆ H ₈ O ₄	144	28564-83-2	Hydroxy or Carbonyl
17.348	32.06	5-Hydroxymethylfurfural	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	126	67-47-0	Alcohol
23.877	1.68	1,2,3-Benzenetriol	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	126	87-66-1	Hydroxy
25.526	1.21	Beta-D-Glucopyranose, 1,6-anhydro	C ₆ H ₁₀ O ₅	162	498-07-7	Acid
29.543	61.37	Quinic acid	C ₇ H ₁₂ O ₆	192	77-95-2	Acid
35.029	0.36	Butanoic acid, octyl ester	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200	110-39-4	Acid
35.788	0.45	n-Hexadecanoic acid	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256	57-10-3	Acid
39.615	0.46	cis-13,16-Docosadienoic acid	C ₂₂ H ₄₀ O ₂	336	7370-49-2	Acid

Table 1. Major bioactive Compounds identified in methanolic fruit extract of *G. pinnata*

In term of % peak area, 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl (2.40 %), 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural (32.06 %), 1,2,3-Benzenetriol (1.68 %), Beta-D-Glucopyranose, 1,6-anhydro (1.21%), Quinic acid (61.37 %),

Butanoic acid, octyl ester (0.36%), n-Hexadecanoic acid (0.45%) and cis-13,16-Docosadienoic acid (0.46%) were found as Eight major Compounds in methanolic extract of *Garuga pinnata* Roxb.

Figure 2

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8

Figure 2.a) 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl **b)** 2,4-Dihydroxy-2,5-dimethyl-3 (2H)-furan-3-one
Figure 3.a) 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural **b)** 2(5H)-Furanone,4-methyl-5-(2-methyl-2-Propenyl) **c)** Furan,2,3-dihydro-4-(1-methylpropyl)-, (S)
Figure 4.a) 1,2,3-Benzenetriol **b)** 3-Methyl-2-furoic acid
Figure 5.a) beta-D-Glucopyranose, 1,6-anhydro **b)** 1,6-Anhydro-beta-d-talopyranose **c)** D-Allose
Figure 6.a) Quinic acid **b)** Butanoic acid,octyl ester **c)** 9-oxabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-2-one, 6-hydroxy **d)** Hexanoic acid, 2-ethylhexyl ester **e)** 6-Hydroxy-9-oxa-bicyclo [3.3.1]nonan-3-one
Figure 7. a) n-Hexadecanoic acid **b)** Pentadecanoic acid.
Figure 8. a) cis-13,16-Docasadienoic acid **b)** (R)-(-)-14-Methyl-8-hexadecyn-1-ol **c)** 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z) **d)** Cis, cis- 7,10,- Hexadecadienal

Table 2. Minor bioactive Compounds identified in Methanolic fruit extract of *G. pinnata*

Compound Analyzed	Molecular Formula	Mol.Wt. (In grams)	CAS No.	Functional Group
2,4-Dihydroxy-2,5-dimethyl-3 (2H)-furan-3-one	C ₆ H ₈ O ₄	144	10230-62-3	ester
Furan,2,3-dihydro-4-(1-methylpropyl)-, (S)-	C ₈ H ₁₄ O	126	34379-54-9	Ketones
2(5H)-Furanone,4-methyl-5-(2-methyl-2-Propenyl)-	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₂	152	89902-24-9	Hydroxy
1,2,4-Benzenetriol	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	126	87-66-1	Hydroxy
3-Methyl-2-furoic acid	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	126	4412-96-8	Acid
1,6-Anhydro-beta-d-talopyranose	C ₆ H ₁₀ O ₅	162	0-00-0	Acid
D-Allose	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	180	2595-97-3	aldehyde
Butanoic Acid,octyl ester	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200	110-39-4	Acid
9-oxabicyclo[3.3.1]nonan-2-one, 6-hydroxy-	C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₃	156	35570-54-8	Acid
Hexanoic acid, 2-ethylhexyl ester	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228	16397-75-4	Acid
6-Hydroxy-9-oxa-bicyclo [3.3.1]nonan-3-one	C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₃	156	0-00-0	Acid
1-(+)- Ascorbic acid 2,6-dihexadecanoate	C ₃₈ H ₆₈ O ₈	652	28474-90-0	Acid
Pentadecanoic acid	C ₁₅ H ₃₀ O ₂	242	1002-84-2	Acid
(R)-(-)-14-Methyl-8-hexadecyn-1-ol	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O	252	64566-18-3	Carbonyl
9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280	60-33-3	Acid
9,12-Octadecadien-1-ol,(Z,Z)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O	266	506-43-4	aldehyde
Cis, cis- 7,10,- Hexadecadienal	C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O	236	56829-23-3	aldehyde

DISCUSSION

The identified major compounds possess some important biological potential for future drug development. The Quinic acid is predominant followed by Alcoholic compounds, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural. The compound Quinic acid with highest % peak area (61.37%) has previously been reported for antioxidant, antidiabetic, anticancer, antimicrobial, antiviral activity. (Bhandari *et al.* 2021). Hydroxymethylfurfural was reported to show

anticancer activity against cancer cells by induction of cell apoptosis (Joel, O and Maharjan, R. 2021). D-Allos has been shown Anticancer, anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, antihypertensive and immunosuppressant activity. n-Hexadecanoic acid possesses some biological activity such as antioxidant, hypocholesterolemic, nematicide and pesticide activity. Pentadecanoic acid has antibacterial and anti-fungal activity. The above-mentioned isolated compounds from the methanol extract of *Garuga pinnata* fruits seem to

possess the reported biological activity (Murali *et al.* 2013) and further study of these phytoconstituents may prove the medicinal importance in future.

CONCLUSION

In present study, many compounds were detected, which were rich in bioactive volatile compounds. Among these volatile compounds some are represents functional group of hydroxy, carbonyl, acid, keton, esters and aldehyde. The major compounds noticed were Quinic acid, Hexadecanoic acid, 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural, 1,2,3-Benzenetriol, beta-D-Glucopyranose, 1,6-anhydro. Hence, the presence of some of the important bioactive volatile compounds will certainly prove the use of extract of selected wild edible plant parts for the preparation of soaps, shampoos, shaving cream, cosmetics, varnishes, detergent, grease etc. because of the presence of such volatile compounds in selected parts of wild edible plants, these may be highly demanded in the pharmaceutical and food industries (Mahadkar S.D and Jadhav V. 2018).

Garuga pinnata is a plant, traditionally used for the treatment of stomach problem, asthma, pulmonary infections, bone fractures, obesity, opacities in conjunctivitis. But till date, there are no reports on chromatographic analysis of methanolic extract of the plant. Here in, we first time report the presence of some important compounds in this plant isolated by GC-MS analysis. Thus, this type of study may give information on nature of active principles present in the wild edible plants and to identify the plants from their adulterants using isolated compounds as biomarker.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors are thankful to the principal and Management of S.D. Arts, V.S. Apte Commerce and M.H.Mehta Science College for providing necessary facilities to carry out the entire research work.

REFERENCES

1. Bhandari, R., Gyawali, S., Aryal N., Gaire D., Paudyal K., Panta A., Panth P., Joshi D.R., Rokaya R.K., Aryal P. and Pandey J. (2021): "Evaluation of Phytochemical, Antioxidant, and Memory-Enhancing Activity of *Garuga pinnata* Roxb. Bark and *Bryophyllum pinnatum* (Lam) Oken. Leaves" The Scientific world Journal, Research Article, Volume 2021, Article ID 6649574.
2. Ghosh., G, Panda ,P., Rath, M., Pal, A., Sharma, T and Das, D., (2015): "GC-MS analysis of bioactive compounds in the methanol extract of *Clerodendrum viscosum* leaves". Pharmacogony Research Journal 7(1): 110-113.
3. Gopu, C., Chirumamilla, P., Daravath S, Vankudoth S and Taduri S (2021): "GC-MS analysis of bioactive compounds in the plant parts of methanolic extracts of *Momordica cymbalaria* Fenzl" Journal of Medicinal plants studies, 9(3):209-218.
4. Joel, O and Maharjan, R., (2021): "Effects of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural isolated from *Cola hispida* on Oral adenosquamous carcinoma and MDR *Staphylococcus aureus*". Journal of Medicinal plant and Herbal Therapy Research, JMPHTR 8 (2021)1-7, ISSN 2053-1826.
5. Kanthal, L. K, Dey A, Satyavathi K and P. Bhojaraju (2014): "GC-MS Analysis Of Bio-Active Compounds In Methanolic Extract of *Lactuca Runcinata* DC" Pharmacogony Research Journal, 6(1):58-61.
6. Mahadkar, S., Valvi, S and Jadhav, V., (2012): "Gas chromatography mass spectroscopic (GCMS) analysis of some bioactive compounds form five medicinally relevant wild edible plants". Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and clinical Research. Vol 6. ISSN no.0974-2441.
7. Mahadkar, S.D and Jadhav, V., (2018): "GC-MS Screening of Some Bioactive Compounds

From Methanolic Extract of Medicinally Relevant Wild Edible Plant Parts” *International journal of scientific research in science and technology* Vol.4, print ISSN:2395-6011.

8. Mehta, B.K., Nigam, V., Nigam, R and Singh, A.,(2012): “GC-MS analysis of the hexane extract of the *Syzygium cumini*” *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* Vol.6 (25):4163-4166.
9. Murali, K.T., Reddy P. N., Pardhasaradhi, M., Ventka, R.B., Singara, C. M..A., (2013) : “Studies on Anticancer and Antibacterial Potentialities of *Garuga pinnata roxb*” *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 21(2), Jul – Aug 2013; n° 30, 163-167, ISSN: 0976 – 044X.
10. Thorat, P.P., Solunke, N.D and Ughade, J. D., (2021): “GC-MS analysis of bio-active compounds in methanolic extract of *Lactuca runcinata DC*” *International Journal of current microbiology and applied sciences*,10 (10): ISSN :2319-7706.
11. Velmurugan, G. and Anand, S. P., (2017): “GC-MS analysis of bioactive compounds on ethanolic leaf extract of *Phyllodium pulchellum L.Desv.*”. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and phytochemical Research* 9(1): 114-118.

HOW TO CITE: Rudrakshi B. Raut*, Shivprasad D. Mahadkar, Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis of Bioactive Compounds in Methanolic Fruit Extract of *Garuga pinnata Roxb*, *Int. J. in Pharm. Sci.*, 2023, Vol 1, Issue 9, 347-354. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8349373>